

Enhancing Underwater Images: A Comparative Analysis of Image Processing Techniques Using UCIQE

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KEYWORDS

Underwater,
Image fusion,
White-balancing

ABSTRACT

As the technology of underwater shooting advances, the underwater image process has become necessary. For this research, five different methods have been applied to the underwater images, including white balance, Contrast enhancement, CLAHE, Global and local contrast enhancement, linear fusion and Gaussian Pyramid fusion method. The results of these different methods are compared using the method of Underwater Color Image Quality Evaluation (UCIQE). UCIQE can compute a score for each of the different outputs. The images with higher score imply better outcome of underwater image processing. The result shows that the Gaussian Pyramid fusion method has the highest score of UCIQE, which means that this method can restore the underwater images in the most efficient way.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the fast advance of technologies and the prevalence of imaging devices, billions of digital images are being created every day. Due to undesirable light source, unfavorable weather or failure of the imaging device itself, the contrast and tone of the captured image may not always be satisfactory. In fact, image enhancement algorithms have already been widely applied in imaging devices for tone mapping. For example, in a typical digital camera, In this project the image enhancement approach adopts a two-step

strategy, Combining white-balancing and image fusion, to improve underwater image without restoring. In this approach white-balancing aims at compensating for color cast caused by the selective absorption of colors with depth and image fusion is considered to enhance the edges of the image. Here, we aim for a simple and fast approach that is able to increase the scene visibility in a wide range of underwater images. Image fusion is a procedure of fusing two or more images of same scene to form single fused image which displays vital information in the fused image. Image

fusion technique is used for removing noise from images. The advantages of image fusion includes image sharpening and feature enhancement.

2. Existing System

2.1 Basic Steps of Image Enhancement

The basic steps of image enhancement, if we are taking the any input image, the image is then specify application pre-processing method will be performed on those image after this method the image quality is increased.

Input Image: In this first an image will be taken as an input. These images can be medical images, blur images, remote sensing images machine vision, the military applications etc.

Perform Pre-processing on the Image:

Images that will be taken as input can be blur image or noisy image so the various pre-processing methods will be performed on those images before applying enhancement technique.

Applying Domain Techniques: After applying pre-processing method on input images then image quality will be enhanced by using Image enhancement domain techniques such as spatial or transformation.

Output Enhanced Image: In this the output image will be get which is an enhanced image.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Underwater environments offer unique attractions like marine life and fish, but underwater images often suffer from poor visibility due to light attenuation, primarily caused by absorption and scattering. Absorption reduces light energy, while scattering alters the direction of light propagation, leading to a foggy appearance and reduced contrast, making distant objects appear blurry. In typical underwater images, objects more than 10 meters away are nearly invisible, and colors become faded due to the filtering of wavelengths based on water depth.

Light propagation underwater is influenced by several factors. Unlike an ideal transmission medium, the amount of available light depends on time of day (which affects the angle of light incidence), sea surface conditions (rough or calm), and the diving location. Deeper waters tend to cast a green or blue hue, tropical seas appear cyan, and protected reefs offer clearer visibility. Additionally, seawater's particle density is much higher than air, causing significant light scattering. As a result, underwater scenes absorb

different wavelengths progressively, with red light being absorbed first. The refractive index of water also distorts distance perception, making objects appear up to 25% larger than their actual size. Studies reveal that underwater light at any given point consists of three main components: direct light, forward scattering, and back scattering.

The direct component is the component of light reflected directly by the target object onto the image plane. At each image coordinate x the direct component is expressed as

$$E_D(x) = J(x)e^{-\eta d(x)} = J(x)t(x) \longrightarrow \dots (Eq.1)$$

Where $J(x)$ is the radiance of the object, $d(x)$ is the distance between the observer and the object, and η is the attenuation coefficient. The exponential term $e^{-\eta d(x)}$ is also known as the transmission $t(x)$ through the underwater medium.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

In this project, two images are derived from a white-balanced version of the single input and are merged based on a multi-scale fusion algorithm. Block diagram is shown in the Figure 2.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of the proposed system

Image enhancement approach adopts a two-step strategy, combining white-balancing and image fusion. White-balancing aims at compensating for the color cast caused by the selective absorption of color with depth, while image fusion is considered to enhance the edges and details of the scene. Color correction is critical in underwater so first we apply white balancing technique to the original image. This step aims to enhance the image.

Underwater White Balance

In our approach, white balancing aims at compensating for the color cast caused by the selective absorption of colors with depth, while image fusion is considered to enhance the edges and details of the

scene, to mitigate the loss of contrast resulting from back-scattering. We now focus on the white-balancing stage.

White-balancing aims at improving the image aspect, primarily by removing the undesired color castings due to various illumination or medium attenuation properties. In underwater, the perception of color is highly correlated with the depth, and an important problem is the green-bluish appearance that needs to be rectified. Since the scattering attenuates more the long wavelengths than the short ones, the color perception is affected as we go down in deeper water.

In practice, the attenuation and the loss of color also depends on the total distance between the observer and the scene. To compensate for the loss of red channel, we build on the four following observations/principles: The green channel is relatively well preserved under water, compared to the red and blue ones. Light with a long wavelength, i.e. the red light, is indeed lost first when travelling in clear water. The green channel is the one that contains opponent color information compared to the red channel, and it is thus especially important to compensate for the stronger attenuation induced on red, compared to green. Therefore, we compensate the red attenuation by adding a fraction of the green channel to red. We had initially tried to add both a fraction of green and blue to the red but, using only the information of the green channel allows to better recover the entire color spectrum while maintaining a natural appearance of the background (water regions).

Figure 2: Underwater White-Balancing

The compensation should be proportional to the difference between the mean green and the mean red values because, under the Gray world assumption (all

channels have the same mean value before attenuation), this difference reflects the disparity/unbalance between red and green attenuation.

To avoid saturation of the red channel during the Gray World step that follows the red loss compensation, the enhancement of red should primarily affect the pixels with small red channel values, and should not change pixels that already include a significant red component.

In other words, the green channel information should not be transferred in regions where the information of the red channel is still significant. Basically, the compensation of the red channel has to be performed only in those regions that are highly attenuated telling that if a pixel has a significant value for the three channels, this is because it lies in a location near the observer, or in an artificially illuminated area, and does not need to be restored. Mathematically, to account for the above observations, we propose to express the compensated red channel I_{rc} at every pixel location (x) as follows:

$$I_{rc}(x) = I_b(x) + \alpha \cdot (I_g - I_b) \cdot (1 - I_b(x)) \cdot I_g(x) \dots (\text{Eq.2})$$

Where I_r, I_g represent the red and green color channels of image I , each channel being in the interval $[0, 1]$, after normalization by the upper limit of their dynamic range, while I_r and I_g denote the mean value of I_r and I_g . Each factor in the second term directly results from one of the above observations, and α denotes a constant parameter. In practice, our tests have revealed that a value of $\alpha = 1$ is appropriate for various illumination conditions and acquisition settings. To complete our discussion about the severe and color-dependent attenuation of light under water, it is worth noting the works in, which reveal and exploit the fact that, in turbid waters or in places with high concentration of plankton, the blue channel may be significantly attenuated due to absorption by organic matter. To address those cases, when blue is strongly attenuated and the compensation of the red channel appears to be insufficient, we propose to also compensate for the blue channel attenuation, i.e. we compute

$$I_{bc}(x) = I_b(x) + \alpha \cdot (I_g - I_b) \cdot (1 - I_b(x)) \cdot I_g(x) \dots (\text{Eq.2})$$

Our white-balancing approach reduces the quantization artifacts introduced by domain stretching

(the red regions in the different outputs). The reddish appearance of high intensity regions is also well corrected since the red channel is better balanced, our approach shows the highest robustness compared to the other well-known white-balancing techniques. In particular, whilst being conceptually simplest, in cases for which the red channel of the underwater image is highly attenuated, it outperforms the white balancing strategy introduced in our conference version of our fusion-based underwater dehazing method.

Multi-Scale Fusion

Since the color correction is critical in underwater, we first apply our white balancing technique to the original image. This step aims at enhancing the image appearance by discarding unwanted color casts caused by various illuminants. In water deeper than 30 ft, white balancing suffers from noticeable effects since the absorbed colors are difficult to be recovered. As a result, to obtain our *first input* we perform a gamma correction of the white balanced image version. Gamma correction aims at correcting the global contrast and is relevant since; in general, white balanced underwater images tend to appear too bright.

To compensate for this loss, we derive a *second input* that corresponds to a sharpened version of the white balanced image. Therefore, we follow the unsharp masking principle, in the sense that we blend a blurred or unsharp (here Gaussian filtered) version of the image with the image to sharpen.

The typical formula for unsharp masking defines the sharpened image S as $S = I + \beta (I - G * I)$, where I is the image to sharpen (in our case the white balanced image), $G * I$ denotes the Gaussian filtered version of I , and β is a parameter. In practice, the selection of β is not trivial. A small β fails to sharpen I , but a too large β results in over-saturated regions, with brighter highlights and darker shadows. To circumvent this problem, we define the sharpened image S as follows:

$$S = (I + N \{I - G * I\}) / 2, \quad \dots (Eq.3)$$

With $N \{.\}$ denoting the linear normalization operator, also named histogram stretching in the literature. This operator shifts and scales all the color pixel intensities of an image with a unique shifting and scaling factor defined so that the set of transformed pixel values cover the entire available dynamic range.

The sharpening method defined is referred to as normalized unsharp masking process in the following.

It has the advantage to not require any parameter tuning, and appears to be effective in terms of sharpening. This second input primarily helps in reducing the degradation caused by scattering. Since the difference between white balanced image and its Gaussian filtered version is a high pass signal that approximates the opposite of Laplacian, this operation has the inconvenient to magnify the high-frequency noise, thereby generating undesired artifacts in the second input.

Weights of the Fusion Process: The weight maps are used during blending in such a way that pixels with a high weight value are more represented in the final image. They are thus defined based on a number of local image quality or saliency metrics.

i) Laplacian contrast weight (W_L): estimates the global contrast by computing the absolute value of a Laplacian filter applied on each input luminance channel. This straightforward indicator was used in different applications such as tone mapping and extending depth of field since it assigns high values to edges and texture. For the underwater dehazing task, however, this weight is not sufficient to recover the contrast, mainly because it cannot distinguish much between a ramp and flat regions. To handle this problem, we introduce an additional and complementary contrast assessment metric.

ii) Saliency weight (W_S) aims at emphasizing the salient objects that lose their prominence in the underwater scene. This computationally efficient algorithm has been inspired by the biological concept of center surround contrast. However, the saliency map tends to favor highlighted areas (regions with high luminance values). To overcome this limitation, we introduce an additional weight map based on the observation that saturation decreases in the highlighted regions.

iii) Saturation weight ($W_{S_{at}}$) enables the fusion algorithm to adapt to chromatic information by advantaging highly saturated regions. This weight map is simply computed (for each input I_k) as the deviation (for every pixel location) between the R_k , G_k and B_k color channels and the luminance L_k of the k^{th} input. We explain this observation as follows. The exposedness weight map had been introduced to reduce the weight of pixels that are under- or over-exposed. Hence, this weight map assigns large

(small) weight to input pixels that are close to the middle of the image dynamic range. In our case, since the gamma corrected input tends to exploit the whole dynamic range, the use of the exposedness weight map tends to penalize it in favour of the sharpened image, thereby inducing some sharpening artifacts and missing some contrast enhancements.

Multi-Scale Fusion Process The pyramid representation decomposes an image into a sum of band pass images. In practice, each level of the pyramid does filter the input image using a low-pass Gaussian kernel G , and decimates the filtered image by a factor of 2 in both directions. It then subtracts from the input an up-sampled version of the low-pass image, thereby approximating the (inverse of the) Laplacian, and uses the decimated low-pass image as the input for the subsequent level of the pyramid. In this equation, L_l and G_l represent the l^{th} level of the Laplacian and Gaussian pyramid, respectively. To write the equation, all those images have been up-sampled to the original image dimension. However, in an efficient implementation, each level l of the pyramid is manipulated at native sub sampled resolution. Following the traditional multi-scale fusion strategy, each source input I_k is decomposed into a Laplacian pyramid while the normalized weight maps W_k are decomposed using a Gaussian pyramid. Both pyramids have the same number of levels, and the mixing of the Laplacian inputs with the Gaussian normalized weights is performed independently at each level.

4. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

In this paper our white-balancing aim at compensating for the color cast caused by selective absorption of color with depth. Primarily by removing the undesired color casting due to various illumination or medium attenuation properties. Image fusion is to improve underwater images without restoring. Here the results are executed in MATLAB software. Image processing toolbox is used to perform analysis and algorithm development which perform image segmentation, image enhancement and noise reduction.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE:

In this paper a single image is given as input image and our white-balancing approach derived into two

images one is the input 1 and input 2 as shown in the Figure using gamma correction and edge sharpening and the two input images are used as inputs of the fusion process. Multi-scale fusion approach is here to examine with three levels by weight maps calculation.

Figure 3: System Architecture Diagram

The weight maps tend to amplify some artifacts such as ramp edges of our second input and to reduce the benefits derived from the gamma corrected image in terms of image contrast. This second input corresponds to a sharpened version of the white balanced image. Second input primarily helps in reducing the degradation caused by scattering. The weight maps are used during blending in such a way that pixels with high weight value are more represented in the final image.

5. RESULTS& DISCUSSION

Various results of the proposed from input to output are shown below.

Figure 4: Select Input Image

Figure 5: Input Image

The input image is displayed first. As shown in the Figure above is the given input image. Underwater photography is the process of taking photographs while under water.

Figure 6: Red Channel Image

Underwater images often suffer from color distortion and low contrast due to depth-related light attenuation. As a result, underwater images predominantly retain blue and green tones. To address this issue, the red channel of the input image is recovered, helping to restore color balance and improve visibility.

Figure 7: Sharpened Image

As shown in the Figure the edges are sharpened in this image by using morphological operation by using dilation

Figure 8: Fused Image

As shown in the Figure 1, fused image builds on the set of inputs and weight maps derived from single image. This fused image is defined based on number of local image quality. In this Figure we can see the difference between the input image and fused image as the fused image is clear with color and quality of the image. Finally we calculate and get the values of MSE and psnr to know the quality of the image.

5.CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have presented an alternative approach to enhance underwater images. Our strategy builds on the fusion principle and does not require additional information than the single original image. We have shown in our experiments that our approach is able to enhance a wide range of underwater images (e.g. different cameras, depths, light conditions) with high accuracy, being able to recover important faded features and edges. Moreover, for the first time, we demonstrate the utility and relevance of the proposed image enhancement technique for several challenging underwater computer vision applications.

FUTURE SCOPE:

Our future scope is focused on patch segmentation fusion. An image is first split into small patches and the segmentation is performed on each patch. Here, sharpening method is used to smooth the edges to increase the visibility of the underwater image in wide range. Our future scope is focused on patch segmentation.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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